

SIMPLIFIED ANALYSIS OF CABLE-STAYED AND EXTRADOSED BRIDGES

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ABSTRACT

Bridges play a key role in all transportation networks. In the current scenario, with the increase in traffic, their significance is increasing day by day. Cable-stayed/ extradosed bridges have emerged as a competitive solution whenever medium spans need to be covered. These are relatively new structural forms and lack proper design standards for their analysis and design. Further, a greater number of design variables are involved so analysis and design become tedious, and intuition does not work. In the present work, an attempt is made to develop a unified simplified analysis approach for cable-stayed and extradosed bridges utilizing continuous beams supported on springs. The stiffness method is used to analyse the beam incorporating the contribution of pylon and cable stiffness and subsequently cable tension evaluation is done while keeping the desired bridge profile as a target. The analysis is verified using the cases reported in the literature as well as using the results of numerical analysis carried out using MIDAS.

Keywords: Cable-stayed bridge, Extradosed Bridge, MATLAB, MIDAS

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Cable Stayed and Extradosed Bridges

Cable-stayed and extradosed bridges are non-linear, indeterminate structural systems in which the inclined cables support the girder flexibly at various points along their length and these cables are supported by a tower. The structural system consists of three main sub-systems: Stiffening girder, tower, and inclined cables. These elements interact to provide an efficient structural behaviour and aesthetically pleasing solution for medium-span (100 m – 600 m) structures.

The structural components of these systems behave in the following manner: The load is transmitted to the tower by the stiffening girder via the cables, which are always under tension. The stiffening girder experiences both axial force and bending. The load is primarily transmitted axially by the tower to the foundation.

1.2 Literature Review

Mermigas (1) in his thesis provided some insights into relationships between various geometric parameters like tower height, girder depth, pier dimension, etc., and the structural behavior, cost, and viability of an extradosed bridge. A comparative study was conducted to demonstrate the differences in material quantities and structural properties of extradosed girder and cable-stayed bridges. The thesis includes the design of four different bridges, including two cantilever-constructed girder bridges, an extradosed bridge with a stiff girder, and an extradosed bridge with a stiff tower, and examines the effects of side span length, deck depth, and stiffness of tower on cable stress variation and deck bending moment.

Fleming (2) discusses the different non-linearities associated with cable-stayed bridges. Under typical design loads, the overall load-displacement relationships for a cable-stayed bridge structure will be nonlinear even though the material in the member acts in a linear elastic fashion. This nonlinear behaviour is caused by the following: large displacements that may occur in the structure under

normal design loads; nonlinear axial force-deformation relationships for the bending members, which may occur due to the interaction of large bending and axial deformations in the members; and the nonlinear axial force-deformation relationship for the inclined cable stays, which may occur due to the sag caused by their dead weight.

A finite element computational approach is proposed in the paper by Wang et al. (3) to compute the initial form of cable-stayed bridges under the influence of girder dead load and pretension in inclined cables. To minimize the deflection and smooth the bending moments in the girder, shape iterations were performed by considering geometric nonlinearities, including large deformation effects, beam-column effects, and cable sag.

1.3 Objective and Scope

The main objective of this paper is to develop a simplified unified approach to determine the preliminary cable tension in cables of both cable-stayed and extradosed bridges under dead load.

The cables are one of the key parts of cable-stayed and extradosed bridges. It takes on most of the load in cable-stayed bridges and a reasonable share in extradosed bridges. When a cable-supported structure is built, rational cable forces can ensure its safety and have a profound impact on the distribution of loads across the bridge components. Therefore, the determination of preliminary cable tension is one of the important steps in the design of any cable-supported structure.

Although many scholars have done a lot of research on the initial cable tension determination of cable-stayed bridges, there is very little work available on extradosed bridges. Extradosed bridge is supported by cables only at specific regions, unlike cable-stayed bridge which is supported by cables throughout the deck. Due to the large unsupported length and limited cable-supported region, simplified methods like “continuous beam on rigid supports” and “beam on elastic foundation” where the whole deck is assumed to be supported on elastic media do not apply to the extradosed bridge.

A stiffness method-based MATLAB program is developed to analyse a plane cable-stayed/extradosed bridge as a continuous beam supported on flexible supports (springs) replacing cables. The program reads input data regarding the geometry, and sectional properties of the system, and for a given dead load, it obtains.

- i) Preliminary cable tension based on iterations by keeping the desired bridge profile as a target.
- ii) Bending moment, axial force, and shear force for both deck and towers.

Behavioural aspects like deck stiffness, axial deformations of the pylon, cable sag, and beam-column effect in the deck which have significant effects on the performance of the bridge are taken into consideration in this approach.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Development of Unified Approach

The deck is analysed as a continuous beam supported by springs at cable anchorage locations and subjected to dead load. The component of spring reaction in the cable direction gives the first estimation of initial cable tension. Based on the deflection profile of the deck obtained in the first estimate, point loads were applied at the spring location and again a deflection profile of the deck which was now subjected to dead load and point loads was obtained. The correction was made to the point loads according to the deflection profile of the deck and analysed again. This iterative process was continued until a desired deck profile was obtained.

Parameter $\beta = \frac{\sqrt{d_1^2 + d_2^2 + d_3^2 \dots}}{n}$ is used as a convergence function to stop the iterations, where d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots are the deviations of the actual profile from the desired profile at each cable location and n is the number of cables. After β has attained a certain value close to zero iterations are stopped. After the final iteration, a component of vertical force in the direction of the cable gives the required cable

tension. Ernst's effective modulus of elasticity is used to consider the nonlinear effect of cable sag. Bending deformations of the pylon due to the horizontal component of cable tension are considered and correction was applied to cable tension based on the change in strain in cable. Beam-column effect in the deck was taken into consideration by modifying the stiffness matrix. To execute the described procedure, a stiffness method-based program was developed in MATLAB.

2.2 Formulation of Spring Stiffness

The stiffness of elastic supports is determined by using corresponding cable stiffness and also by considering the effect of axial shortening of the tower as per Troitsky (4).

Fig. 1. Elastic support spring constant

ΔT - axial shortening of the tower due to cable tension P

ΔL – Elongation in the cable due to cable tension P

Total vertical deflection, $\Delta V = \Delta L/\sin(\alpha) + \Delta T$

$$\Delta V = \frac{P.L_c}{A_c E_c \sin \alpha} + \frac{P \sin \alpha \cdot h}{A E_{\text{pylon}}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Flexible support stiffness } K = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{L_c}{A_c E_c \sin^2 \alpha}\right) + \left(\frac{h}{A E_{\text{pylon}}}\right)} \quad (2)$$

2.3 Non-linear Effects

Cables in cable-supported bridges are generally long. As a result, due to its weight and an axial tensile force, it sags into catenary shape. Because the change in cable sag does not vary linearly with cable tension, sag leads to a nonlinear force-deformation relationship. By using the effective modulus of elasticity, it is possible to model the cables as straight members between the anchorage points as per Walter and Scalzi (5).

$$E_{eff} = \frac{E_i}{1 + \frac{(A E_i) \cdot w^2 \cdot L_0^2}{12 \cdot T^3}} \quad (3)$$

The general form of equilibrium equations are $[K]\{U\} = \{F\}$, where $[K]$ is stiffness matrix, $\{U\}$ and $\{F\}$ are vectors of joint displacements and applied force respectively. To consider the nonlinear beam-column effect, a modified stiffness matrix that depends on the axial load is utilized which changes

with each iteration as the cable tension changes (Chajes (6)). Here, L_e represents effective length of the element under consideration and P is axial force in the element.

$$[K]_{mod} = [K] - P * \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{6}{5L_e} & \frac{1}{10} & 0 & \frac{-6}{5L_e} & \frac{1}{10} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{10} & \frac{2L_e}{15} & 0 & \frac{-1}{10} & \frac{-L_e}{30} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-6}{5L_e} & \frac{-1}{10} & 0 & \frac{6}{5L_e} & \frac{-1}{10} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{10} & \frac{-L_e}{30} & 0 & \frac{-1}{10} & \frac{2L_e}{15} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

2.4 Backstay Cables

Back-stay cables are a special feature in cable-stay bridges which are used to transfer the loads directly to the abutment from the tower. They are subjected to max stress changes due to live loads on the deck. To indirectly sustain the central portion of the main span that is unbalanced by the side span, the initial back stay forces are calculated by equating their horizontal components to the horizontal components of corresponding stay cable forces of the main span, as suggested by Shenawy (7).

After finding the preliminary cable tensions, based on the bending deformation of the pylon a correction was applied to the cable forces of the back-stay cables to make the deflection at top most point zero.

2.5 Demonstration of Simplified Approach

An extradosed bridge model available in the literature is utilized to demonstrate the procedure. As this is a symmetric bridge, variation of cable tension with each iteration was demonstrated for a set of cables associated with one pylon (in this case 18 cables). Cables are denoted as C1, C2...C18, and C1 referring to the cable farthest to the pylon in the side-span and C18 is the farthest cable from the pylon in the mid-span.

Fig. 2. Elevation of the extradosed bridge

Fig. 3. Bridge deck as continuous beam on springs

Fig. 4. Cable tension in cables after different iterations

The above plots demonstrate the variation in cable tension after different iterations. There is a sudden jump in the trend from the initial estimate to 1st iteration and thereafter convergence in the cable forces was obtained. With each iteration, the deflection profile of the deck gets closer and closer to the desired profile, and the corresponding correction in cable tension was also reduced. Therefore, convergence can be seen in the cable tensions.

Fig. 5. Deflection profile of deck after different iterations

Fig.5 shows the effectiveness of the corrections applied to cable tensions by displaying the deflection profile of the deck obtained after a certain number of iterations. The maximum deflection obtained from the first estimate of cable tension is beyond the permissible limit and as cable tension changes, the deflection profile of the deck approaches the desired deck profile (In this case it is a horizontal profile without any camber).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To verify this unified approach, we took examples of two symmetric cable-stayed bridges and two symmetric extradosed bridges available in the literature. The effectiveness of this approach was judged by comparing the cable forces obtained from this method with the cable forces available in the paper and the corresponding deflection profiles of the deck were obtained from MIDAS. Upper and lower permissible limits of deflection were also plotted to show the validity of the deflection profiles obtained.

The results are as follows.

- i) Symmetric harp cable-stayed bridge from the paper by Wang et al. (3).

Table 1. Properties of the symmetric harp cable-stayed bridge

Geometric properties	
Main Span	335.28m
Side span	137.16m
Pylon height	60.96 m
Dead load	87.56kN/m
Section Properties	
Deck	$I = 1.13\text{m}^4$; $A = 0.3193\text{m}^2$
Pylon	$I = [0.432 \ 0.3452 \ 0.211]\text{m}^4$ (bottom to top) $A = [0.269 \ 0.227 \ 0.202]\text{m}^2$ (bottom to top)
Material Properties	
Deck	Steel; $E = 210000\text{MPa}$
Pylon	
Cables	

Fig. 6. Elevation of the symmetric harp cable-stayed bridge

Fig. 7. a) Deflection profile of deck b) Comparison of cable tensions

ii) Symmetric Fan extra dosed bridge from the thesis by Shenawy (7).

Configuration and geometric properties of the bridge are shown in Fig. 2 of section 2.4. Section and material properties are as follows

Table.2. Properties of the symmetric fan extradosed bridge

Section properties	
Deck	$I = 25.843\text{m}^4$; $A = 17.649\text{m}^2$
Pylon	$I = 134.13\text{m}^4$; $A = 26.404\text{m}^2$
Material Properties	
Deck	M50; $E = 35000\text{MPa}$
Pylon	M50; $E = 35000\text{MPa}$
Cables	$E = 200000 \text{MPa}$

Fig. 8. a) deflection profile of deck b) Comparison of cable tensions

iii) Symmetric fan cable-stayed bridge from the thesis by Shenawy (7).
properties of the bridge are

Table 3. Properties of the symmetric fan cable-stayed bridge

Geometric properties	
Main Span	300m
Side span	110m
Pylon height	70m
Dead load	600kN/m
Section Properties	
Deck	$I = 25.843\text{m}^4$; $A = 17.649\text{m}^2$
Pylon	$I = 134.13\text{m}^4$; $A = 26.404\text{m}^2$
Material Properties	
Deck	M50; $E = 35000\text{MPa}$
Pylon	M50; $E = 35000\text{MPa}$
Cables	$E = 200000\text{MPa}$

Fig. 9. Elevation of symmetric fan cable-stayed bridge

As it is a symmetric bridge, only the cable forces corresponding to the left pylon were shown. As shown in Fig.8, C1 corresponds to the farthest cable from the pylon in the side span, C24 corresponds to the farthest cable from the pylon in the main span, and C2 to C23 denote cables in the same order.

Fig. 10. a) deflection profile of deck b) Comparison of cable tensions

iv) Symmetric harp extradosed bridge from the thesis by Mermigas (1)
Preliminary cable tensions under dead load were not provided in the thesis, therefore the cable forces obtained from the simplified method were compared with the cable forces obtained using the MIDAS cable tension determination tool.

Table 4. Properties of the symmetric harp extradosed bridge

Geometric properties	
Main Span	140m
Side span	84m
Pylon height	14m
Dead load	290kN/m
Section Properties	
Deck	$I = 10.7804\text{m}^4$; $A = 9.0135\text{m}^2$
Pylon	$I = 7.15\text{m}^4$; $A = 7\text{m}^2$
Material Properties	
Deck	M50; $E = 28100\text{MPa}$
Pylon	M50; $E = 28100\text{MPa}$
Cables	$E = 200000\text{MPa}$

Fig. 11. Elevation of symmetric harp Extradosed bridge (figure not drawn to scale)

Fig. 12. a) deflection profile of deck b) Comparison of cable tensions

4. SUMMARY

The preliminary design of cable-supported bridge involves steps like assuming variables like number of spans, back span to main span ratio, deck depth, pylon height, cable spacing, etc, and then determining the preliminary cable tension and form of the deck. Preliminary design is an important stage, it gives the first approximation for the sections required in the numerical models as the input data. Simplified methods provide quick, approximate but rational results that can guide initial design decisions. Therefore, a unified and simplified procedure was developed in this paper to determine the preliminary cable tension. The method is computationally effective and considers most of the behavioural aspects of deck, cables, and pylon. The effectiveness of this method was demonstrated by comparing the results obtained with some of the examples available in the literature. It is acknowledged that cable tensions obtained from the proposed method may differ from those reported in existing literature. However, the fact that the resulting deflection profile is within the permissible limits reinforces the validity of the proposed method. The proposed method offers a simplified yet reliable alternative for determining preliminary cable tensions in cable-stayed and extradosed bridges and can be utilized in development of optimization tools for getting competitive design.

REFERENCES

- (1) **Mermigas, Konstantinos Kris.** *Behaviour and design of extradosed bridges*. University of Toronto 2008.
- (2) **Fleming, John F.** *Nonlinear Static Analysis of Cable-Stayed Bridge Structures*. Computers & Structures, Vol. 10, pp 621-635, 1979.
- (3) **Wang, P. H., Tseng, T. C., & Yang, C. G.** *Initial shape of cable-stayed bridges*. Computers & Structures, Vol. 47, pp 111-123, 1993.
- (4) **Troitsky, M. S.** *Cable-stayed bridges: Theory and design*. 2nd edition. Oxford: BSP Professional books, 1988.
- (5) **Podolny, W., Scalzi, J. B.** *Construction and design of cable-stayed bridges*. 2nd edition: Wiley-Interscience, 1986.
- (6) **Chajes, Alexander.** *Principles of structural stability theory*. New Jersey: Prentice-hall, Inc, 1974.
- (7) **EL Shenawy, E. A.** *Form finding for cable-stayed and extradosed bridges*. Technical University Berlin. 2013.